

An experiment carried out on the territory of the Fruit Growing Institute - Plovdiv

07 June 2024

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This project receives funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation action under grant agreement No 101000224.

Results of the first experiments of the Fruit Growing Institute - Plovdiv test field

The studies conducted include the following options:

1. Maintenance in black fallow,
2. Grassy area (chim),
3. Fruit-bearing peach plantation maintained in natural mulch.

In the peach orchard, feeding with organic products has been carried out.

In the experiment, three fertilization rates with organic products and a non-fertilized version were tested.

The content of mineral nitrogen (N-NH_4^+ и N-NO_3^-) in the soil samples was determined by the distillation method after extraction with 1% KCl. Mobile phosphorus (P_2O_5) was determined in a lactate extract (DL method) colorimetrically, with a hydrazine sulfate reducer and that of potassium (K_2O) – with a flame photometer. Soil reaction (pH) and electrical conductivity (Ec) were determined potentiometrically in water extract (1:2.5).

The soil is alluvial-meadow for all three areas.

The results obtained for the section maintained in black fallow are presented in a table 1.

Table 1. Agrochemical analysis of soil

Depth, cm	pH (H_2O)	P_2O_5 mg/100g	K_2O mg/100g	NH_4^+ mg/kg	NO_3^- mg/kg
0-30 cm	7.15	59.0	33	34.89	128.0
30-60 cm	8.04	44.8	26	43.33	264.03

Soil reaction was neutral to moderately alkaline. The soil is characterized by very high values for phosphorus, optimal levels for potassium. Mineral nitrogen availability is good.

The obtained results of the section supported in chim are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of the soil

Depth, cm	EC μS	pH (H_2O)	P_2O_5 mg/100g	K_2O mg/100g	NH_4^{4+} mg/kg	NO_3^- mg/kg
0-30 cm	89.50	7.69	12.20	28.50	19.96	21.53
30-60 cm	79.60	7.68	8.00	11.00	18.84	18.84

The soil in the experimental plot of the present study was an alluvial meadow, with a slightly alkaline soil reaction (pH 7.68 – 7.69). Electrical conductivity varied within 79.60 to 89.5 $\mu\text{S}/\text{cm}$. The content of phosphorus and potassium in the plantations ranged from low to medium stocking rate. The amount of mineral nitrogen in both soil profiles varied from 18.84 to 21.53, indicating that the soil was low in nitrogen. The results of the analyses show that the soil in the plantation was average stocked with the main macroelements.

The agrochemical soil properties in a fruiting peach orchard at the beginning of the experiment are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Soil supply in the peach plantation with the major nutrients

Depth, cm	pH (H ₂ O)	P ₂ O ₅ mg/100g	K ₂ O mg/100g	NH ₄ ⁺ mg/kg	NO ₃ ⁻ mg/kg
Control					
0-30 cm	7,16	19,8	23	21,73	15,55
30-60 cm	7,13	30	20	25,4	15,03
Biohumus					
0-30 cm	7,1	26	32,6	13,24	19,23
30-60 cm	7,3	31	23	11,14	18,14
Agrifull					
0-30 cm	7,05	22	30	12,96	16,07
30-60 cm	7,43	155	20	13,22	15,81
Humustim					
0-30 cm	7,24	66	27,4	16,33	20,99
30-60 cm	7,28	160	21	11,92	19,18

The soil in the experimental plot is alluvial-meadow, with a soil reaction from neutral to slightly alkaline (Tabl. 3). There are significant differences in the supply of soil with phosphorus. According to the margin levels of supply (20-30 mg P₂O₅/100 g), all the samples fall under the category of highly supplied. Very high supply was reported for the rows fertilized with Agrifull and Humustim at a depth of 30-60 cm. The amount of mineral nitrogen varied by variants of fertilization. The potassium content in the experimental plot varied from 20 to 32.6 mg/100 g of soil. The control falls under the category of moderately supplied.

Table 4. Phosphorus and potassium content and soil reaction in water extract and in 1N KCl after fertilization with bioproducts

Fertilization rate	pH(H ₂ O)		pH (KCl)		P ₂ O ₅ mg/100g		K ₂ O mg/100g	
	0-30 cm	30-60 cm	0-30 cm	30-60 cm	0-30 cm	30-60 cm	0-30 cm	30-60 cm
Biohumus								
40 kg/da	7,19 ab	7,83 a	6,40 ab	7,15 ab	29,33 ab	51,00 a	25,13 bc	16,93 bcd
80 kg/da	6,70 b	7,19 bc	6,04 b	6,13 b	41,00 ab	69,13 a	26,00 bc	15,80 cd
120 kg/da	7,40 a	7,94 a	6,79 a	7,13 ab	75,80 a	80,93 a	43,13 a	17,93abcd
Agrifull								
0.5 L/da	7,07 ab	7,37 ab	6,29 ab	6,22 b	44,6 ab	62,07 a	31,3 abc	18,47abcd
1.0 L/da	6,73 ab	7,60 ab	6,06 ab	6,74 ab	16,67 b	54,00 a	22,47 c	18,00abcd
Humusim								
100 ml/da	6,65 b	7,67 ab	5,97 b	7,04 ab	8,93 b	58,13 a	23,47 c	13,00 d
120 ml/da	6,64 b	7,41 ab	5,78 b	6,50 ab	14,0 b	91,00 a	27,67 bc	18,50 abc
150 ml/da	6,86 ab	7,74 ab	6,24 ab	7,24 ab	15,13 b	52,33 a	40,67 a	21,67 ab
Amoniev nitrat								
22 kg/da	4,89 c	6,72 c	4,30 c	6,33 ab	7,27 b	27,97 a	27,33 bc	19,00 abc
Control	6,72 b	7,71 ab	6,06 b	7,46 a	19,23 b	88,00 a	36,27 ab	22,83 a

The electrical conductivity ranged from 244 μS to 811 μS for the 0-30 cm layer and from 124 μS to 250 μS for the 30-60 cm layer in the different variants of fertilization. Soil electrical conductivity was relatively high, although below the threshold for damage to the peach trees (Tabl. 3).

Table 3. Ammonium nitrogen and nitrate nitrogen content and soil electrical conductivity after fertilization with bioproducts

Fertilization rate	Ec, μS		N-NH ₄ ⁺ mg/kg		N-NO ₃ ⁻ mg/kg	
	0-30 cm	30-60 cm	0-30 cm	30-60 cm	0-30 cm	30-60 cm
Biohumus						
40 kg/da	305,33 ab	163,33 b	6,40 c	26,84 b	37,85 c	7,91 b
80 kg/da	811,33 a	211,33 b	133,45 ab	6,04 ab	146,00 ab	28,97 ab
120 kg/da	244,33 b	181,00 b	19,87 c	6,79 ab	16,90 c	5,79 b
Agrifull						
0.5 L/da	292,67 ab	124,67 b	32,15 bc	13,90 ab	39,49 bc	9,27 b
1.0 L/da	402,00 ab	207,33 b	46,93 bc	18,83 ab	66,34 bc	16,02 b
Humusim						
100 ml/da	297,67 ab	184,33 b	36,69 bc	14,09 ab	44,80 bc	7,72
120 ml/da	177,33 b	135,00 b	22,79 c	15,93 ab	16,99 c	11,68 b
150 ml/da	224,67 b	200,00 b	19,79 c	14,87 ab	15,06 c	13,79 b
Amoniev nitrat						
22 kg/da	655,67 ab	539,00 b	181,93 a	33,22 a	187,34 a	56,10 a
Control						
	262,33 b	250,33 a	29,26 c	20,28 ab	40,56 bc	11,78 b

Soil reaction was neutral to moderately alkaline. A significant decrease in pH values was observed as a result of fertilization with ammonium nitrate. The pH values in H₂O were 4,89 for the layer 0-30 cm and pH 6,72 at 30-60 cm depth. In KCl salt extract those values were 4,3 (0-30 cm) and 6,33 (30-60 cm). The imported ammonium nitrate led to an acidification of the soil reaction in the surface soil layer.

- ✓ Fertilization of alluvial-meadow soils with high rates of Biohumus led to an increase in the mobile forms of phosphorus in the soil, with a close relation between the rate of fertilization and the amount of the mobile forms of phosphorus, expressed by a linear equation.
- ✓ Despite the high rates of Biohumus and Agrifull fertilizers applied, deep penetration into the soil was not observed.
- ✓ The long-term application of the bioproducts contributed favorably to the soil characteristics of pH, Ec, NO₃⁻, NH₄⁺, P₂O₅, K₂O in the peach plantation and contributed to a favorable supply of nutrients (potassium, phosphorus and nitrogen), optimal for the nutrition of peach trees.
- ✓ Continuous application of ammonium nitrate led to acidification of soil, which is unfavorable to the peach crop.
- ✓ The application of bioproducts to soil confirmed the positive impact on its nutrient supply and hence, increases its productivity.